

INTERFACIAL REACTION AND ITS EFFECT ON THE MECHANICAL
PROPERTY OF SiCp/Al COMPOSITES
H.W.Tsai W.L.Wang G.D.Zhang
Institute of Composite Materials
Shanghai Jiao Tong University
Shanghai 200030
P.R.China

ABSTRACT

SiCp/Al composites manufactured by comocasting method was heated to different temperatures and holded for a certain period in order to change interfacial conditions. Tensile strength of the composites was tested, its composition and microstructure were identified by chemical analysis, optical metallograph, SEM&EDAX and XRD. The relationship between interfacial reaction and mechanical property was discussed.

The results showed that large amount of Si and Al₄C₃ were presented in the matrix alloy as a result of interfacial reaction between SiC particulates and Al alloy. Because of the presentation of Si and impurity element Fe which was mixed during fabrication process, impurity phases Al₆(FeMn)Si blockes were formed. These brittle impurity phases were detrimental to the mechanical property of composites. The degradation of the composites' tensile strength was thus attributed to the Al₄C₃ and Al₆(FeMn)Si phases formed as a result of interfacial reaction between SiCp and Al alloy.

KEYWORDS: Particulate composites; Silicon carbide; Aluminum matrix; Interfacial reaction; Failure mechanism.

1. INTRODUCTION

SiCp/Al composites has been the topic of intensive study in the past several years

all over the world since of its attracting properties such as high specific stiffness, high temperature strength, lower CTE, good wear-resistance, good workability and isotropy[1,2]. Up to today, the fabricating technology of the composites is still one of the most important problem, and the processing parameters of the fabricating technique has a remarkable effect on the mechanical property of the composites therefrom[3,4]. Moreover, the near-net shape casting property of the composites has not yet been understood clearly, only several papers[5,6] concerned with this aspect had been published. As we know that these properties decide directly the use value of the composites. So it is of practical importance to study the fabricating and remelting techniques and its effect on the mechanical property of the composites.

From the viewpoint of industrial scale production, compocasting may be regarded as the most promising fabricating technology of particulate reinforced metal matrix composites. It is a easy-operating and cost-effective process and the composites therefrom is of satisfactory mechanical property. But since the fabricating process is carried out where the Al alloy is in liquid condition, this might cause interfacial reaction between SiCp and Al alloy since of such a high temperature. On the other hand, when near-net shape cast method is employed to form composites components, the SiCp/Al composites will inevitably suffer from high temperature preservation for a certain period, this might also cause more severe interfacial reaction. Interfacial reaction has a detrimental effect on the mechanical property of the composites so measures must be taken in order to prevent the take place of interfacial reaction.

This paper investigated the interfacial reaction between SiCp and Al alloy and its effect on the mechanical property of the composites. SiCp/Al composites was remelted at different temperatures and holded for a certain period, thus to change interfacial reaction degree. Tensile strength of the composites was tested and its relationship with interfacial reaction was discussed. The failure mechanism of the composites was postulated. The interfacial reaction kinetics of the SiCp/Al composites which stated the relationship between the interfacial reaction degree and temperature and time of the process the composites experienced was reported in another paper[7].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

SiCp/Al composites considered in this paper was fabricated by compocasting method which had a matrix of Al-Cu-Mg-Mn alloy (Al-4.4%Cu-1.5%Mg-0.6%Mn, designated LY12) and SiC particulates of nominal size 10um and weight fraction 10wt%. The composites was casted into preheated graphite crucibles after it had been fabricated. The

crucibles were then preserved in a box type oven for a certain period at different temperatures, they were 0.5hr, 1.0hr, 1.5hr, 2.0hr and 973K, 1023K, 1073K, respectively. Ingots obtained above were then extruded with a extrusion ratio of $R_i:R_f=37.5:12$. The extruded bars were subjected to T6 treatment, that is, 773K+1.5hr, water quenched, 353K+8.0hr. Three rod tensile samples for each kind were machined from treated bars.

Tensile test was performed at room temperature using a DCS-2000 universal test machine. Crosshead speed was 0.5mm/min. The microstructures, fracture surfaces of the composites was evaluated on a Neophot-II optical microscopy, a S-520 SEM equipped with an EDAX. The polished specimen were etched using a etchant of 25% nitric acid ethylalcohol. XRD analysis of phase constitution of the composites was carried out on a D/max-IVA diffractometer. Si and Fe concentrations in the composites were determined by colorimetric analysis and Al4C3 by gas chromatography.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Interfacial reaction between SiCp and Al matrix It was found that SiCp would react with liquid Al alloy at the remelting temperature. The phase constitution of the investigated composites were identified by XRD analysis with the results shown in figure 1(a-d). Compared with that of as-fabricated, as shown in figure 1(a), diffraction peak numbers increased obviously in the composites after remelting, as shown in figure 1(c-d). These peaks were identified to be that of Si and Al4C3, two kinds of interfacial reaction products. Thus it was confirmed that SiCp would react with Al alloy in the following way, as had been suggested in several papers:

Furthermore, according to the peak intensities of Si and Al4C3 in figure 1, we found that the amount of interfacial reaction products were also decided by the remelting temperature and holding time. In order to determine the concentrations of Si and Al4C3 in the composites quantitatively, chemical analysis and gas chromatography were employed, with the results shown in figure 2. It was obvious that the results by chemical analysis and by XRD (according to peak intensity) were in well consistent. Also, there was a relationship between the tensile strength degradation extent and the amount of interfacial reaction products in the composites, that is, the more amount of interfacial reaction products, the more degradation on the tensile strength.

FIGURE 1. XRD analysis of the SiC_p/Al composites before and after remelting (●Si, ▲Al₄C₃, ■Al, □SiC)

FIGURE 2. Concentration of Al₄C₃ and Si in the SiC_p/Al composites

3.2 Effect of remelting temperature and holding time on the tensile strength of SiC_p/Al composites The results showed that tensile strength of SiC_p/Al composites would degrade inevitably after remelting at high temperature for a certain period, as shown in figure 3. It was obvious from figure 3 that the remelting temperature had a great effect on the degradation extent of the composites' tensile strength. At lower temperature, holding for a short period would have no noticeable effect on the tensile strength, only a long period preservation would cause a obvious drop on the tensile strength of the composites. On the contrary, since when the composites was preserved at higher temperature, a short period preservation would cause a sharp drop on the tensile strength of the composites, whereas longer period preservation would have no extra effect.

3.3 Microstructure of SiC_p/Al composites The microstructure of the composites before and after remelting changed obviously, see figure 4(a-b). SiC particulates

FIGURE 3. Tensile strength of composites (normalized) after remelting

of originally sharp corners were all rounded and its size reduced after remelting. That is, in one word, dissolution of SiC particulates. There were also large amount of small dark undetermined phases along the SiCp/Al interface and in Al matrix. They were, in some papers, usually said to be Al₄C₃ phases. However, this need further TEM study. Moreover, many large size block phases were presented in the matrix after remelting. In order to have a detailed knowledge of these block phases, polished and etched samples were examined in S-520 SEM using the attachment---EDAX. The results were listed in figure 5(a-c).

FIGURE 4. Optical microstructure of SiCp/Al composites

EDAX analysis of these block phases (marked A as shown in figure 5(b)) indicated that they were all Al-Fe-Mn-Si phases, generally expressed as Al₆(FeMn)Si. It was a kind of brittle impurity phases presented usually in Al alloy and here they had a size scale of about 50-60μm. As a result, these impurity phases might play a important roll on the fracture of the composites, as illustrated in figure 6.

a. as-fabricated

b. 1073k+2.0hr

c. EDAX analysis of block phase in b

FIGURE 5. SEM observation and EDAX analysis of the composites

Fractography of the composites after remelting was shown in figure 6(c), many dark blocks were found on the fracture surface. A careful observation indicated that they were all Al₆(FeMn)Si phases which had a characteristic of cleavage fracture surface. Figure 6(d) showed a typical fracture surface of these impurity phases. No such character was observed on the fracture surface of the as-fabricated composites, with its fractography shown in figure 6(a-b).

a. as-fabricated

b. as-fabricated

c. 1073K+2.0hr

d. 1073K+2.0hr

FIGURE 6. Fractography of SiCp/Al composites

3.4 Concentration of impurity element Fe in the composites In order to confirm these large amount of impurity iron-phases existed in the composites, the Fe concentration was determined, with the results listed in table 1.

TABLE 1. Fe concentration in the SiCp/Al composites

	Fe wt%		
as-fab.	0.55	0.48	0.49
remelted	0.42	0.55	0.46

It was found that during the fabrication process, impurity element Fe was mixed into the composites and therefore the Fe concentration in the obtained ingots was already rather high. No more extra Fe was mixed during succeeded remelting process since of graphite crucible being used. Detailed check of the fabrication process showed that possible Fe sources included furnace burdens (Al ingots, SiC particulates), steel crucible and agitating impeller. So it was very important to control the fabrication process of the composites in order to reduce Fe concentration to a lowest level so that the brittle impurity phases would have no noticeable effect on the tensile strength of the composites. As had been pointed out, impurity element Fe made it possible to form $Al_6(FeMn)Si$ phases.

3.5 Discussion The degradation of the composites' tensile strength after remelting must be contributed to the interfacial reaction taken place during preservation. So the most important problem was the way the interfacial reaction affected on the fracture mechanism of the composites.

It had been found that large amount of Al₄C₃ were formed in the composites since of remelting. This might cause several detrimental effects. The reinforcement SiC particulates might suffer from degradation due to interfacial reaction and the bonding strength between SiCp and Al matrix might be strengthened for the same reason. Because of the brittleness of Al₄C₃ phase, the interface zones might serve as crack initiations when external stress was applied. Moreover, Al₄C₃ had a strong tendency to hydrolyze thus resulted in a severe stress-corrosion crack failure mechanism and on the same time, the corrosion resistance of the composites was accordingly rather poor.

Impurity phases, since of its brittleness, might be regarded as another important factor to affect the tensile strength of composites. These brittle phases had generally a size scale of 50-60um and inevitably served as inclusions to destroy the integrity of matrix alloy. According to the iso-strain model, when external stress was applied, these brittle phases would fracture at first since of its poor ductility. As soon as the cracks were initiated, they would propagate radiatively which resulted in a disastrous failure of the composites. So these phases were wholly detrimental to the mechanical property of the composites. Above inference of the failure mechanism might also be confirmed by the fractography as shown in figure 6(a-d). The fracture surface of as-fabricated composites was a combination of partially even fracture and wedge fracture surface, this indicated a void nucleation and coalescence fracture mechanism, therefore the ductility of the composites was relatively good. That was not the condition for the fracture mechanism of the composites after remelting. Since of such a large amount of Al₄C₃ and Al₆(FeMn)Si phases were presented in the composites, they would be served as crack initiations and thus the composites fractured in a brittle way with an even fracture surface. Detailed investigation indicated that these impurity phases were all appeared in the pit since of its poor ductility, surrounded by ductile Al matrix.

According to the results of Si and Fe concentrations in the composites, we found that they were already sufficiently high to form Al₆(FeMn)Si phases, even though we did not find any, in the as-fabricated composites. This indicated that the main factors affecting the formation of Al₆(FeMn)Si were the remelting temperature and holding time. Since of high temperature and long period preservation of the composites, Fe and Si were activated to form brittle phases. So in order to optimize the mechanical property of SiCp/Al composites, measures must be taken to eliminate the detrimental effect of impurity element Fe and interfacial reaction. Possible solutions were to reduce the Fe concentration to a lower level and prevention of interfacial reaction by alloyment (addition of Si) or control of processing parameters of SiCp/Al composites' fabrication technique.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. SiCp would react with Al alloy during fabrication and remelting process. As a result, Al₄C₃ and Si were formed in the composites, their amounts increased with the increasement of remelting temperature and holding time.

2. Interfacial reaction had a detrimental effect on the mechanical property of the composites. High temperature or low temperature and long period remelting resulted in a sharp drop of the tensile strength of the composites. Only low temperature and short period remelting had no noticeable effect on the tensile strength.

3. Presentation of Al₄C₃ and Al₆(FeMn)Si phases affected the failure mechanism of the composites. These brittle phases might serve as crack initiations and resulted in a disastrous fracture mode of the composites.

5. REFERENCES

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